

THE REFINED 2-D ASYMPTOTIC THEORY FOR THE DYNAMICS OF THE THIN ASYMMETRIC LAMINATES

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ABSTRACT

The modern industries deal mainly with layered constructive elements (CE) of symmetric structure. Despite of this technological tendency the non-symmetric structures themselves are of great interest and often appear in delaminated CE. We investigate here the internal stress-strain state for two groups of thin plates in the long-wave approximation:

1. Arbitrary posed N plies with general anisotropy.
2. Transversely anisotropic plies with large difference in the properties.

The new asymptotic equations are deduced and classified, both separate and coupled bending and in-plane stress-strain state are considered. Then the analysis of engineering hypotheses is based on. The method of solving the static problems is suggested and the examples of non-symmetry influence on the statics and dynamics of laminates are given.

Keywords: laminate, composite, asymmetry, contrast, dynamics.

1. INTRODUCTION

As known the application of inhomogeneous across thickness plates embraces primary modern industries. For optimal design the non-symmetric structures are especially interesting to deal with. Only restrictions of composite technology demand to symmetrize an element. Besides, the non-symmetry appears in delaminated sandwiches and structures with a wide variety of isotropic layers became typical.

Methods based on the engineering hypotheses (Lekhnitski, 1963; Christensen, 1979) and methods of asymptotical integration of 3-D equations of the theory of elasticity (Friedrichs et al., 1961; Goldenweiser et al., 1962; Agalovian, 1966) are mainly used to deduce the 2-D mathematical models for thin-walled structures. The second ones involve more complex considerations and results. But they permit us to determine the limits when hypotheses are available and to calculate the whole tensor of stresses. Generally the problem to approximate the main stress-strain state is divided into internal and boundary layer effects.

Statics of anisotropic laminates of arbitrary structure was partially studied both by engineers (for example, Alfoutov et al., 1984) and mathematics (Caillerie, 1982; method of homogenization). Below the regular dynamic generalization of classical Kirchhoff theory of plates is given.

Some results for plates of isotropic plies with high different properties (alternatively high and low modulus layers) are given by Gussein-Zade (1968, 1970) and Bolotine et al. (1980). Here the dynamic bending is investigated in general statement.

2. MULTILAYERED PLATE OF N ANISOTROPIC PLYS

2.1. General dynamic equations

Let a plate occupy a region $(\mathbf{x}, z \equiv x_3) \in \Omega \times [z_1, z_{N+1}] \subset R^3$ and consist of N anisotropic layers with full contact. Each ply is supposed to have a plane of elastic symmetry, parallel the plane \mathbf{x} , and its thickness, mass density and matrix of stiffnesses are $h_i, \rho_i, G_i = \|g_{pq}\|_i$ respectively. The relation $\varepsilon = h/l$ is introduced now as a unique small parameter for the whole sandwich, where $2h$ is a thickness and l is a scale of process in the longitudinal plane \mathbf{x} with the characteristic time $t_0 = O(\varepsilon^{-1})$. The plate is charged by the exterior surface loading, independent ε , regular with sufficiently weak variation

$$\sigma_{33}^{\pm}(\mathbf{x}, t) = \sigma^{\pm}, \quad \tau_{\beta 3}^{\pm}(\mathbf{x}, t) = \tau_{\beta}^{\pm} \quad (z^{\pm} = z_{N+1}, z_1) \quad (1)$$

By asymptotic integration of 3-D equations of dynamic elasticity we deduce the consistent expressions for the displacements \mathbf{U}, U_3 which coincide with classical theory of plates. The displacements are independent on ply number i . Below we restrict the relative accuracy with members $O(\varepsilon^2)$, the indexes 0, 1 correspond to the normal and tangential loads and will be omitted in evident cases. Then, on introducing the membrane ($k = 1$), membrane-bending ($k = 2$) and bending ($k = 3$) rigidities d_{pq}^k and main operators the final equations result in the form (to sum with repeating greek indices $\alpha, \beta = 1, 2$)

$$U_3 = l\varepsilon^{-3}(W_0 + \varepsilon W_1 + \dots), \quad \mathbf{U} = l\varepsilon^{-2}(\bar{\mathbf{V}}_0 + \varepsilon \mathbf{V}_1 + \dots), \quad \mathbf{V} \equiv (V_1, V_2) \quad (2)$$

$$l\varepsilon^{-3}(W_0 + \varepsilon W_1) = w(\mathbf{x}, t), \quad l\varepsilon^{-2}(\bar{\mathbf{V}}_0 + \varepsilon \mathbf{V}_1) = \mathbf{u}(\mathbf{x}, t) - z \text{ grad } w, \quad \mathbf{x} = \mathbf{i}_{\alpha} x_{\alpha}$$

$$\mathbf{a}_{\beta}(d_{pq}^1)\mathbf{u} - b_{\beta}(d_{pq}^2)w = (\tau_{\beta}^{-} - \tau_{\beta}^{+}), \quad \rho = \sum_i h_i \rho_i / 2h \quad (3)$$

$$\{2h\rho\partial_i^2 + b(d_{pq}^3)\}w - \mathbf{a}(d_{pq}^2)\mathbf{u} = (\sigma^{+} - \sigma^{-}) + \text{div}(z^{+}\boldsymbol{\tau}^{+} - z^{-}\boldsymbol{\tau}^{-}) \quad (4)$$

$$\mathbf{a}_1(\gamma_{pq}) \equiv \mathbf{i}_1[\gamma_{11}\partial_1^2 + 2\gamma_{16}\partial_{12}^2 + \gamma_{66}\partial_2^2] + \mathbf{i}_2[\gamma_{16}\partial_1^2 + (\gamma_{12} + \gamma_{66})\partial_{12}^2 + \gamma_{26}\partial_2^2] \quad (5)$$

$$b_{\beta} \equiv \mathbf{a}_{\beta} \text{ grad}, \quad \mathbf{a} \equiv \partial_{\beta}\mathbf{a}_{\beta} = \mathbf{i}_{\beta} b_{\beta}, \quad b \equiv \partial_{\beta} b_{\beta} = \mathbf{a} \text{ grad} \quad (1 \leftrightarrow 2)$$

$$d_{pq}^k = \frac{1}{k} \sum_i (z_{i+1}^k - z_i^k) \gamma_{pq}^i, \quad \gamma_{pq}^i = (g_{pq} - g_{p3}g_{3q}g_{33}^{-1})_i \quad (pq = 11, 12, 22, 16, 66, 26)$$

The quasistatic Equations 3 resemble a system for the generalized plane stress state (P), the dynamic Equation 4 looks like the bending (B) one in Kirchhoff theory. The influence of an arbitrary plate structure appears in the membrane-bending operators $b_{\beta}, \mathbf{a}(d_{pq}^2)$, i.e., the System 3, 4 is mixed.

Remark. In general another consistent representation $\mathbf{U}_3 = O(\varepsilon \mathbf{U})$ for stretching mode is possible only at the special cases of structures and loading [11]

$$\xi = 0, \quad \sigma^{+} = \sigma^{-}, \quad \text{div}(z^{+}\boldsymbol{\tau}^{+} - z^{-}\boldsymbol{\tau}^{-}) = 0$$

2.2. Classification of coupled bending and in-plane problems

To explain the physical situation we consider the deformations

$$e_{33} = e_{\beta 3} \equiv 0, \quad e_{\alpha\beta} = \varepsilon_{\alpha\beta} + z\kappa_{\alpha\beta}, \quad \varepsilon_{\alpha\beta} = \frac{1}{2}(\partial_{\alpha}u_{\beta} + \partial_{\beta}u_{\alpha}), \quad \kappa_{\alpha\beta} = -\partial_{\alpha\beta}^2 w$$

Generally the in-plane deformations $\varepsilon_{\alpha\beta}$ are no zeros at every longitudinal plane. So, the first hypothesis in Kirchhoff theory is not available because of the absence of neutral plane. As a

criterion of connection between B- and P-problems the integral norm of operators $b_\beta, \mathbf{a}(d_{pq}^2)$ is to be evaluated. It is determined by a usual modulus for the sum of two equivalent four-component vectors of membrane-bending terms. Its minimum ξ gives a fixed position of plane \mathbf{x} ($z = 0$) which coincides with neutral plane for special cases.

$$b_1(d_{pq}^2) \sim \mathbf{B}_1 \equiv (d_{11}^2, 3d_{16}^2, d_{12}^2 + 2d_{66}^2, d_{26}^2), \quad \mathcal{B}(z^-) \equiv (|\mathbf{B}_1|^2 + |\mathbf{B}_2|^2)^{1/2} \geq 0$$

$$z^- \equiv \zeta; \quad \frac{d}{d\zeta} \mathcal{B}(\zeta) = 0, \quad \xi \equiv \mathcal{B}(\zeta) \neq 0 \quad (6)$$

Consequence 1. A laminate of arbitrary structure is characterized by total thickness, mass density and 18 rigidities. Three layered anisotropic sandwich constitutes the more simple equivalent structure. A plate of three differently oriented orthotropic plies is generally not sufficient for this ■

Consequence 2. Stresses, their integrands and energy depend on both kinds of deformations. Equations 3, 4 rewritten in terms of integrands coincide with classical theory ■

$$\sigma_{\alpha\beta} = f_{\alpha\beta}(\gamma)e, \quad Q_{\alpha\beta} = f_{\alpha\beta}(d^1)\varepsilon + f_{\alpha\beta}(d^2)\kappa, \quad M_{\alpha\beta} = f_{\alpha\beta}(d^2)\varepsilon + f_{\alpha\beta}(d^3)\kappa$$

$$N_\alpha = \partial_\beta M_{\alpha\beta}, \quad 2\Pi = \int_\Omega (Q_{\alpha\beta}\varepsilon_{\alpha\beta} + M_{\alpha\beta}\kappa_{\alpha\beta}) d\Omega$$

$$f_{11}(\gamma)e \equiv \gamma_{11}e_{11} + 2\gamma_{16}e_{12} + \gamma_{12}e_{22}, \quad f_{12}(\gamma)e \equiv \gamma_{16}e_{11} + 2\gamma_{66}e_{12} + \gamma_{26}e_{22}$$

The expressions for transversal stresses are more cumbersome and presented in [11, 12].

Then we can divide the main operator \mathcal{D} in Equations 3, 4 into two parts $\mathcal{D}_{13}, \mathcal{D}_2$ (\mathcal{F} is an operator of loading)

$$\mathcal{D}(\mathbf{u}, w) \equiv \mathcal{D}_{13}\mathbf{v} - \xi\mathcal{D}_2\mathbf{y} = \mathcal{F}$$

$$\mathcal{D}_{13} \equiv (\mathbf{a}_1, \mathbf{a}_2, \rho\partial_t^2 + b)^T, \quad \mathcal{D}_2 \equiv \xi^{-1}(b_1, b_2, \mathbf{a})^T, \quad \mathbf{v} \equiv (\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{u}, w)^T, \quad \mathbf{y} \equiv (w, w, \mathbf{u})^T$$

Theorem. The symbols of operators $\mathcal{D}_{13}, \mathcal{D}$ are of elliptic type ■

When $\xi = 0$ the complete separation of B- and P problems is achieved and $b_\beta, \mathbf{a}(d_{pq}^2) \equiv 0$. This improved classical case takes place for the following structures:

1) *Orthotropic layered beam with common main axes.* In the axes x_1, z separated equations are the same as for two homogeneous beam with equivalent bending and membrane rigidities, Poisson's ratios and Young's moduli

$$(B) \quad \nu = d_{12}^3/d_{11}^3, \quad 2E = 3d_{11}^3(1 - \nu^2), \quad (P) \quad \nu = d_{12}^1/d_{11}^1, \quad 2E = d_{11}^1(1 - \nu^2)$$

2) *Plate of plies with transversal isotropy.* In this case two equivalent monoplates are introduced by rigidities $d^k \equiv d_{11}^k = d_{22}^k = d_{12}^k + 2d_{66}^k, d_{\beta 6}^k = 0$ ($d^2 \equiv 0$) and the same formulas for Young's moduli and Poisson's ratios. The transversal anisotropy has no influence on the equations. The only difference of the Cases 1 and 2 from homogeneous structure consists in the presence of membrane forces (B) and bending moments (P) at the plane $z = 0$. Two isotropic plies can simulate these structures for both B- and P problems.

3) *Symmetrically posed anisotropic plies* ($d_{pq}^2 \equiv 0$).

4) *The case of small ξ .* We suggest to search the solution in the recurrent form

$$(\mathbf{u}, w) = \sum_n \xi^n (\mathbf{u}, w)^{(n)}, \quad \mathcal{D}_{13}\mathbf{v}^{(0)} = \mathcal{F}, \quad \mathcal{D}_{13}\mathbf{v}^{(n+1)} = -\mathcal{D}_2\mathbf{y}^{(n)}$$

where the operator \mathcal{D}_{13} is familiar to usual separated B- and P problems to be solved at each step. Such iterative procedure can be investigated in detail by usual methods for perturbed operators, but for small enough ξ the sequence is convergent surely.

2.3. Potentials in statics

For statics the potentials for displacements can describe well the coupled fields and allow to use methods of theory of functions of complex variables. They are defined as follow

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{u} &= \text{Re}[\mathbf{u}^* \Psi(\mathbf{s}\mathbf{x})], \quad w = \text{Re}[u_3 \Phi(\mathbf{s}\mathbf{x})], \quad u_\alpha^*, s_\alpha = \text{Const} \in \mathcal{C}, \quad \mathbf{s} = (s_1, s_2) \\ \mathbf{a}_\alpha \mathbf{u} &= p_{\alpha\beta}^1 u_\beta^* \Psi'', \quad b_\alpha w = p_{\alpha 3}^2 u_3^* \Phi''', \quad \mathbf{a}\mathbf{u} = p_{\alpha 3}^2 u_\alpha^* \Psi''', \quad bw = p_{33}^3 u_3^* \Phi'''' \\ p_{11}^k &= d_{11}^k s_1^2 + 2d_{16}^k s_1 s_2 + d_{66}^k s_2^2, \quad p_{12}^k = d_{16}^k s_1^2 + (d_{12}^k + d_{66}^k) s_1 s_2 + d_{26}^k s_2^2 \\ p_{\alpha 3}^k &= p_{\alpha\beta}^k s_\beta, \quad p_{33}^k = p_{\alpha 3}^k s_\alpha, \quad (s_1 = 1, s_2 = s) \\ \mathbf{P}\mathbf{u}^* &= 0, \quad p \equiv p_0^1 p_{33}^3 - p_{11}^1 (p_{13}^2)^2 - p_{22}^1 (p_{13}^2)^2 + 2p_{12}^1 p_{23}^2 p_{31}^2, \quad p_0 \equiv p_{11} p_{22} - p_{12} p_{21} \end{aligned}$$

Equations 3, 4 are satisfied when $\Psi = \Phi'$, $p(s) = 0$. The function $p(s)$ is polynomial of 8-th order and has four pairs of roots s, \bar{s} (including the multiple roots). Degenerated case is reduced to variants $p_0^1(s) = 0$, $\mathbf{a}\mathbf{u} = 0$ and $p_{33}^3(s) = 0$, $b_\alpha w = 0$. At $\xi = 0$ we obtain $p \equiv p_0^1 p_{33}^3$ and independent potentials Ψ, Φ coincide with classical results [1].

Remark. Dispersion curves for monochromatic waves which propagate as $\exp[i(\omega t + \mathbf{s}\mathbf{n}\mathbf{x})]$, $\mathbf{n} = (\cos \theta, \sin \theta)$ is given by the equality

$$2h\rho\omega^2 p_0^1(\mathbf{n}) = s^4 p(\mathbf{n}) \quad (7)$$

The strict investigation of the interaction of boundary layer with internal stress-strain state is of great interest. A coupled model demands 4 boundary conditions at $\partial\Omega$. The most natural ones are combined of classical B- and P statements. From the engineering point of view they can be deduced easy by variational principles for energy II.

2.4. Examples of structure influence on the stress-strain state

Much significant influence of structure is obvious at simple analytical solution already:

1) *In Statics* we can refer to the case of elliptic laminate with fixed edges. When the loads are decomposed into power series with terms as $g_{ml} x_1^m x_2^l$ the solution is found elementary for any polynomial components $\sigma^+ - \sigma^- = \sigma_{M-1}$, $\tau^\pm = \tau_M^\pm$. Its general representation is:

$$\mathbf{u} = \mathbf{u}_M f, \quad w = w_{M-1} f^2; \quad \partial\Omega: f \equiv x_\alpha^2 / c_\alpha^2 - 1 = 0 \quad (M = 0, 1, \dots)$$

($\mathbf{u}_M, \tau_M^\pm, w_{M-1}, \sigma_{M-1}$ are polynomials of fixed orders where $m + l = M$ or $M - 1$). Then at the contour $\partial\Omega$: $\mathbf{u} = 0$, $w = 0$, $\partial_n w = 0$ and from the Equations 3,4 we establish a linear system of $3M + 2$ equations with $2(M + 1) + M$ unknown coefficients g_{ml} for displacements. The matrix of system contains all combinations of rigidities.

2) *In Dynamics* the dependence of free oscillations on structure is shown for beam with fixed edges $x_1 = \pm L$. The frequencies are taken from the Formula 7, where $\mathbf{n} = (0, 1)$, $s = \lambda/L$, and $th\lambda \pm tg\lambda = 0$. In the case of two orthotropic plies $0^\circ + \theta/90^\circ + \theta$ (at $\theta = 0^\circ, 90^\circ, \dots$ the separate P-solution is quasistatic) with ratios $\nu_{12} = 0.3$, $E_1/E_2 = 10 \sim 20$, $G_{12}/E_1 = 0.1 \sim 0.05$ all frequencies vary as follow

$$\delta(\theta) + 1 \equiv \omega(\theta)/\omega(0^\circ), \quad \min \delta(\theta) = \delta(45^\circ) \equiv \Delta, \quad \Delta = 0.1 \sim 0.2$$

3. LAMINATE OF HIGH INHOMOGENEOUS ISOTROPIC LAYERS

Primary bending motions of plates with arbitrary hierarchy of isotropic (or transversal isotropic) layers are considered below. Large differences in thicknesses, Young's moduli and sound velocities are taken into account as additional small parameters.

3.1. Physical assumptions and general 2-D equations

Now the plate consists of N isotropic homogeneous elastic layers and it is moving under action of facing loads (1). The high contrast constitution of the plate cross-section is defined by asymptotic equalities:

$$e_i = \varepsilon^{p_i} E_{max}/E_i = O(1), \quad C_i = \varepsilon^{q_i} c_i^2/c_{min}^2 = O(1), \quad H_i = h_i/h = O(\varepsilon^{r_i}), \quad t_0 = O(\varepsilon^\gamma)$$

$$E_{max} = \max_{i \in I} E_i \equiv \max E_i, \quad c_{min} = \min c_i, \quad c_i^2 = E_i/\rho_i, \quad i \in I = \{i: 1 \leq i \leq N\}$$

where $p_i, q_i, r_i \geq 0$ are known non-negative indexes of laminae contrasts, t_0 denotes characteristic time and γ will be evaluated below. The values $\nu_i, 1 - 2\nu_i$ are not assumed to be very small. We introduce non-dimensional functions and independent variables, represent each function in power series with respect to transversal coordinate, substitute all of them in the dynamic 3-D problem and reduce a new system of equations to an equivalent recurrent form. Then we construct 2-D approximate equations with a relative error $O(\varepsilon^2)$ restricted by the first iteration. This accords to the accuracy of ordinary Kirchhoff's type theories. Naturally, the accuracy achievable by different edge conditions for high inhomogeneous limited plate is too complicated question to answer and we do not touch it here. But before the reduction of the equations we have to limit the index values γ, p_i, q_i in order to discount some unpractical models and to fulfill our assumption $\varepsilon \ll 1$. The elimination of short bending waves yields the restriction $\gamma \leq 1/2$. Indexes p_i, q_i can be restricted by practical considerations. In result, we take into account the estimations:

$$0 \leq p_i \leq 3, \quad 0 \leq q_i \leq 2, \quad \gamma \leq 1/2 \quad (8)$$

The values r_i have no restrictions. We propose then the following asymptotic evaluations for unknown functions:

$$U_3^i = w(\mathbf{x}, t) + O(\varepsilon^n w), \quad \mathbf{U}^i = O(\varepsilon^k w), \quad (k, n \geq 1) \quad (9)$$

Physically, the Relations 9 indicate a nondeflection of the normal across the whole section. The tangential displacement is asymptotically small in comparison with the normal one. In fact, they are necessary for the beginning of recurrent process and can be verified *a posteriori*. Finally, we write a complete system of approximate equations for the $2N + 1$ functions w and u_β^i :

$$Lw \equiv (D\Delta^2 + 2h\rho\partial_t^2)w = A_i^\circ \Delta \operatorname{div} \mathbf{u} + q_3^- + h \operatorname{div} \mathbf{q}^+ \quad (10a)$$

$$A_i \Lambda_{i\beta} \mathbf{u}^i = -q_{\beta 3}^-; \quad q_{\alpha 3}^\pm = \sigma_{\alpha 3}^+ \pm \sigma_{\alpha 3}^-, \quad \mathbf{q} = (q_{13}, q_{23}) \quad (10b)$$

$$u_\beta^i = u_{\beta*} + b_i \tau_\beta^m + \sum_{j \in I} \Gamma_{ij}^m \Lambda_{j\beta} \mathbf{u}^j - G_i^m \partial_\beta \Delta w \quad (10c)$$

$$U_\beta^i = u_\beta^i + z(\mu_i^{-1} \sigma_{\beta z_0}^i - \partial_\beta w) + O(\varepsilon^2 u_\beta^i), \quad U_3^i = w + O(\varepsilon^2 w), \quad p_i - r_i \leq 2 \quad (10d)$$

$$U_3^i = w + W^i(\mathbf{x}, t) + z\sigma_{z_0}^i/(\lambda_i + 2\mu_i) + O(\varepsilon^2 w), \quad 2 < p_i - r_i \leq 3 \quad (10e)$$

$$D = \frac{d_i}{3}(z_{i+1}^3 - z_i^3), \quad A_i^\circ = \frac{A_i}{2} \sum_{j \in I} h_j \operatorname{sgn}(i - j), \quad z_{j+1/2} = \frac{1}{2}(z_j + z_{j+1})$$

$$2\Lambda_{i\beta} \mathbf{u} = (1 + \nu_i) \operatorname{div} \partial_\beta \mathbf{u} + (1 - \nu_i) \Delta u_\beta, \quad \alpha = 1, 2, 3$$

$$b_i = \sum_{k \in K} B_k^{-1} \operatorname{sgn}(i - i_*) - \mu_i^{-1} z_{i+\theta}, \quad \Gamma_{ij}^m = A_j G_{ij}^m, \quad G_i^m = \sum_{j \in I} A_j z_{j+1/2} G_{ij}^m$$

$$G_{ij}^m = \sum_{k \in K} B_k^{-1} H_{kj}^m \operatorname{sgn}(i_* - i) + \mu_i^{-1} z_{i+\theta} H_{ij}^m, \quad m = -, +; \quad i_- = i, \quad i_+ = i + 1$$

$$K = \{k: k = i_* + 1, \dots, i - 1, i > i_* + 1; k = i_* - 1, \dots, i + 1, i < i_* - 1; \emptyset, i = i_*, i_* \pm 1\}$$

$$H_{kj}^- \equiv H_+(k - j) = \{0, k \leq j \text{ or } 1, k > j\}$$

$$H_{kj}^+ = -H_+(j - k); \quad \theta = H_+(i_* - i); \quad A_k = d_k h_k, \quad B_k = \mu_k h_k^{-1}$$

$$d_i = E_i / (1 - \nu_i^2), \quad \lambda_i + 2\mu_i = (1 - \nu_i)E_i / (1 - 2\nu_i)(1 + \nu_i), \quad \mu_i = E_i / 2(1 + \nu_i)$$

Here $\sigma_{\alpha 0}^i$ is the first term of the row for $\sigma_{\alpha z}^i$ [13], $\mathbf{u}_* \equiv \mathbf{u}^i$, $i = i_*$; i_* is a number of the reference ply which is defined as a rigid ply ($p_i = 0$) having maximal thickness. There are two equivalent forms of (10c) at $m = \pm$. Besides, we have proved that the Equations of the in-plane problem 10b,10c are quasistatic. The location of a middle imitate plain or center of bending is defined from the equality (the former membrane-bending main term in (8b) is equal to zero)

$$\sum_{i \in I} d_i (z_{i+1}^2 - z_i^2) = 0$$

Using Equations 8,9 we can establish that in the range $0 \leq p_i - r_i \leq 2$, $0 \leq q_i \leq 2$, $i \in I$ the eliminated terms in (10a) are $O(\varepsilon^2)$ and $O(\varepsilon)$ in the "membrane" Equations 10b,10c. If $2 \leq p_i - r_i \leq 3$ for some soft laminae then corrections $W^i = O(\varepsilon^n w)$, $1 \leq n < 2$ in (10e) due to the influence of transversal deformation must be introduced. In comparison with Timoshenko type theories only the terms corresponding to the influence of longitudinal shear appear in (10). The mutual influences of stretching, shear and bending connect the equations. The Limits 8 are very wide and therefore our 2-D theory possesses some excessive complication as the price of generality. At the particular sets p, r, q the system are variously simplified. As a rule, the essential simplifications are connected with possibility of separate description for the flexion and in-plane deformation.

3.2. Classification of degenerate-inhomogeneous structure models

Local and mini-maximum asymptotic orders of functions can be evaluated and on this basis the restrictions for indexes p_i, r_i are established when Kirchhoff's assumptions either remain actual or break in turn. Besides absolute maximums of p_i, q_i, r_i and their sums the mutual position of various layers is important for structure behavior as a whole. We identify three classes of plates and, consequently, the models of behavior.

First class. It is well known that very soft external laminae have no influence on the bending of a whole plate. It is possible to give a general description for hierarchies of soft plies surrounding a kernel of rigid laminae when the main equations are the same as in the improved classical theory.

The second class is physically characterized by the existence of several kernels of rigid plies connected by not very soft laminae. Then terms with $\Lambda_{j\beta} \mathbf{u}^j$ can be neglected in (8c). The main equations are divided into a six order equation for w and usual ones with perturbed right-hand side for \mathbf{u} :

$$\begin{aligned} (D_0 \Delta^3 + L)w &= q_3^- + \operatorname{div}(h\mathbf{q}^+ - A^o A^{-1} \mathbf{q}^-) \\ (A_i \Lambda_{i\beta})u_{\beta*} &= -q_{\beta 3}^- + (A_i G_i^m) \Delta^2 \partial_\beta w, \quad D_0 = (A_i^o G_i^m) - (A_i G_i^m) A^o / A \\ u_\beta^i &= u_{\beta*} + \left(\frac{z}{\mu_i} \sum_{j \in J_m} e_j A_j \operatorname{sgn}(i - j) - G_i^m \right) \Delta \partial_\beta w - z \partial_\beta w \\ J_- &= \{j: 1 \leq j < i\}, \quad J_+ = \{j: i < j \leq N\} \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

Although the equations are separated the problem remains connected because of lateral boundary conditions. Instead of (11) the Equations 10 without the second and third terms in the right-hand side of Equation 10c can be used.

The third class is formed by the plates with some very soft intermediate laminae. Equations 10 remain connected and have the highest order but they can be simplified for the particular cases.

4. CONCLUSION

The 2-D mathematical models for the dynamics of non-symmetric high inhomogeneous or anisotropic elastic plates have been presented. In general, bending and stretching are strongly connected. Different modifications have been separated and classified. In particular, the improved classical theory of layered plates has been followed. Then bending and in-plane motions are separately described in spite of dynamics, differences in Poisson's ratios and other properties. That is a substantiation of the engineering approaches, but all the stresses have been determined in the present way. The suggested classification depends on the type of anisotropy, mutual lamina locations and the contrasts of layers. The classes of plates when the theory turns out no more complicated than the classical one are described.

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